

Exhibit Repository System for Accreditation

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Abstract - *The study aimed to develop an Exhibit Repository System for Accreditation (ERSA) that will serve as repository and manage digital documents for accreditation patterned to the parameters set by the Accrediting Agency of Chartered Colleges and Universities in the Philippines (AACCCUP). The system was tested for its: (1) functional document and exhibits management for accreditation with two-factor authentication in wired and wireless network; (2) acceptability and user-friendly graphical user interfaces; (3) software quality; (4) performance in terms of functionality, performance efficiency, compatibility, usability, reliability, security, maintainability, and portability. This study was conducted during the AY 2017-18 at Northern Iloilo Polytechnic State College (NIPSC), Ajuy Campus, Ajuy, Iloilo. The waterfall model was used for software development. The systems repository is browser-based, stored and configured in intranet setting. There are 33 respondents. McCall's Software Quality Criteria for IT experts and the ISO /IEC 25010:2011 SQuARE Criteria for end-users were used in testing the structure, functions, and features of the system. The statistical tools used in data analysis were the frequency distribution, percentage, and mean. The findings revealed that ERSA has a very good performance, functional document and exhibit management, multi-platform, multiuser, secured, user-friendly and worked in the wired and wireless network. Therefore, ERSA collects, stores, and presents exhibits in the form of digitized documents that uses latest ICT technologies and has features and modules that satisfy the requirements of the system users and should be adapted and used by state universities and colleges (SUCs) to help in their accreditation preparations and exhibits presentation.*

Keywords – Accreditation, Exhibit, Repository, System

INTRODUCTION

It is the policy of the State to protect, conserve, promote and popularize the nation's historical and cultural heritage and resources. It shall pursue, conserve and promote the Filipino cultural heritage and resources including the documentary records of Filipino culture, history, and governance. It shall give utmost priority for the safeguard, protection, and preservation of its public documents and records, not only as fundamental instruments for efficient and effective governance but also as essential tools for the preservation of the country's history and cultural memory (RA 9470).

Towards this end, all public records with enduring value, held by government offices, including, but not limited to, all branches of government, constitutional offices, local government units (LGUs), government-owned-and-controlled corporations (GOCCs), state universities and colleges (SUCs), Philippine embassies, consulates, and other Philippine offices abroad shall be transferred to a permanent government repository for proper management, control and regulation of record disposition (RA 9470).

Furthermore, it is also a declared policy of the State to encourage and assist, through the Commission on Higher Education (CHED), higher education

institutions (HEIs), which desire to attain standards of quality over and above the minimum requirements by the State, thus, for this purpose, the CHED encourages the use of voluntary non-governmental accreditation system in aid of the exercise of its regulatory function (CMO 1-2005).

On the other hand, the environment is abundantly growing technologically. This attitude is expected if we consider the rapid scientific and technological strides for the last one hundred years which has brought about comforts and convenience to the modern man in particular, and the global development and prosperity in general.

And realizing the fact that the future of human society is inextricably linked with information and communications technology (ICT) and the computer is the heart of ICT while information is at the heart of every policy decision, activity, interaction and transaction among stakeholders themselves. It has emerged as very useful and potent tool in almost everything, and as stipulated in the 1987 Philippine constitution, it gives cognizance to ICT's role in nation building as provided for in Article II, Section 24, to wit: "The State recognizes the vital role of communication and information in nation-building".

Therefore, this study is based on the premise that accreditation is an important requisite to ensure that the education provided by institutions of higher education meets acceptable levels of quality for curricular programs and accreditation should be revolutionized using the latest ICT technologies. The status of accreditation of any state university or college will have a lasting impact on the delivery of quality education. And it is the goal of every HEIs in order to evaluate its educational activities, in whole (institution) or in part (by program), by seeking judgment to confirm whether it has substantially achieved its objectives and is generally at par or comparable with other institutions in terms of quality education. The process leads to a grant of accredited status by an accrediting agency and provides public recognition and information on educational quality.

Today, member HEIs of all accrediting agencies generally undertakes the same process familiar to many quality assurance methodologies: (1) a self-study using a survey designed to fit their organizational or program profile, followed by (2) an on-site review by a team of trained and experienced accreditors. CHED Order No 31 of 1995 remains in effect, and complements the efforts of the accrediting agencies by progressive deregulation and the granting of benefits, in line with its membership status within the accrediting agency.

In SUCs, there are ten (10) criteria (areas) that are used in the assessment of programs: (1) Vision, Mission, Goals, and Objectives (VMGO); (2) Faculty; (3) Curriculum and Instruction; (4) Students; (5) Research; (6) Extension and Community Involvement; (7) Library; (8) Physical Plants and Facilities; (9) Laboratories; and (10) Administration and in each criterion there are parameters to be accomplished.

In every accreditation, members of the Accreditation Taskforce prepare all relevant and sufficient documents to support benchmark statements in the criterion set by AACCUP. These documents are in the form of information and can be put into an electronic form and stored in a computer as one or more files. Historically, document management required the use of paper. Without this, it would very difficult to conduct business and document management can also be costly when unmanaged, a notable scenario can be observed during an accreditation of academic programs. The taskforce has difficulty in producing, duplicating, updating and consolidating exhibits and doing these in loads of hard-copied documents, cost arises and having different storage locations require separate office space, separate manpower to manage it, separate security measures to implement, and separate accessibility level.

In general, all of the processes in accreditation are done manually and all the records are maintained on papers. So, the maintenance of records is very difficult, very frustrating and the existing system is monotonous, time-consuming, less flexible, and provides a very hectic working schedule, thus, result processing is slow due to paperwork and requirements of the taskforce.

But with information revolution bringing the server into business operations, everything changed. For the first time, businesses could store, organize and maintain documents electronically, the birth of personal computer (PC), the electronic document management system (EDMS), the search engine, the scanner, the cloud and the smartphone. Each new development added resources, depth, usefulness, and efficiency to document management systems. And sooner or later, physical DMS will be entirely obsolete in the accreditation process, EDMS will revolutionize it.

Thus, Exhibit Repository System for Accreditation (ERSA) promises a productivity and performance increases by applying new technology to documents and document processing in particular, ERSA will serve as a digital repository that will manage the scanning, uploading, storing, duplicating, tagging, archiving and retrieving digital documents for accreditation.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aims to develop an Exhibit Repository System for Accreditation that will serve as a digital repository and manage the scanning, uploading, storing, duplicating, tagging, archiving and retrieving of digital documents for accreditation.

Specifically, it aims to: (1) develop a repository system that manages documents and other exhibits for accreditation with two-factor authentication that can be used in wired and wireless network; (2) design a repository system that has an acceptable and user-friendly graphical user interfaces; (3) determine the software quality of the proposed features of the Exhibit Repository System for Accreditation by the experts based on McCall's Quality Software Criteria; and (4) evaluate the performance of the proposed features of Exhibit Repository System for Accreditation as perceived by the respondents based on the following: (a) functionality, (b) efficiency, (c) compatibility, (d) usability, (e) reliability, (f) security, (g) maintainability, and (h) portability.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study utilized the descriptive-developmental research design. Descriptive in the sense that it

described characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied and developmental because the study involves designing and developing a system and was conducted at the Northern Iloilo Polytechnic State College, Ajuy Campus, AY 2017-18.

The Waterfall Model was used as the software development model and the system's repository is browser-based, stored and configured in intranet setting that can run in the wired and wireless network.

Preliminary Investigation and Data Gathering Tools.

An important part of a study is the selection of data gathering tools. It is crucial because the whole study relied on the information gathered using these tools. The following are the tools that were used by the researcher:

Unstructured Interview. An unstructured interview was conducted because it is flexible and open. The questions asked were determined by the research problem and objectives, the contents, sequence, and wordings are up to the interviewer. The researcher converted user stories into iterations that cover a small part of the functionality or features required. A combination of iterations provides the stakeholder with the final fully functional product.

Unstructured Observation. An unstructured observation was also observed to the taskforce; this type of observation is open and flexible which provides a richer and more direct description of the phenomena under investigation. In this method, the researcher was not restricted by an observation guide. The researcher's watched and recorded behaviors, events, and situations guided by the problem and objectives of the investigations.

Document Analysis. The researcher gathered data relevant to its course of study. The researcher-system analyst analyzed the collected exhibits from the member of the accreditation team, by area, so that different media type can be configured in the best way to convert it to digital format for archiving.

System Design Phase

The following are the system/ data analysis tools used in this study.

Data Flow/ Context Diagram. Through data flow diagram, the researcher-system analyst put together the graphical representation of data processes throughout the system. The data flow approach emphasized the logic underlying the system. The researcher-system analyst able to create a pictorial depiction of the processes that eventually provided solid system documentation.

Use Case Diagram. This tool helped the researcher-system analyst identified the functional requirement, users, and their accessibility level on the system.

Entity-Relationship Diagram (ERD). This tool is used to define the relationship, roles, and cardinalities between different entities so as to show how tables were used together with other tables that are related to each other.

Data Dictionary. This tool is use to identify the structure of the database and its corresponding tables, data types can be assigned.

Implementation Phase

Software Development Tools. The system was developed using different client-side technologies such as HTML for the foundation of web pages, cascading style sheets (CSS 3.0) for the styles, format, and layout of the pages, javascript for interactivity and validation. Server-side technologies include Laravel and Hypertext preprocessor (PHP 7) for interacting with the database, MySQL Community Server for the storage of records and Apache Server to manage all the services needed.

Sitemap. A sitemap is a list of pages of a web site accessible to crawlers or user.

Application Architecture Model. A multi-tier application architecture was employed to logically separate the different application-specific, operational and data-centric layers.

System Testing Phase

Software Testing. Software testing was performed to verify that the completed software package functions according to the expectations defined by the requirements/ specifications.

Debugging. Debugging was used to in locating and fixing or bypassing bugs (errors) in computer program code.

Research Instrument. The study utilizes the McCall's Quality Model for expert testing and ISO (International Organization for Standardization) /IEC (International Electrotechnical Commission) 25010:2011 Systems and software engineering - Systems and software Quality Requirements and Evaluation (SQuaRE) - System and software quality models for user testing distributed to the purposive population. A 5-point Likert scale comprising of 1 as Poor and 5 as Very Good was used to the developed system prototype.

The obtained mean scores for user acceptance and expert testing were interpreted using the following guide:

Mean Score	Verbal Interpretation
4.21-5.00	Very Good
3.41-4.20	Good
2.61-3.40	Average
1.81-2.60	Fair
1.00-1.80	Poor

Respondents/ Software Evaluators. The respondents of the study were the three (3) experts, two (2) internal accreditor, one (1) accreditation director, and the twenty-seven (27) accreditation taskforce members. There was a total of 33 respondents using the purposive sampling.

Statistical Tools. The statistical tools used in data analysis were the frequency distribution, percentage, and weighted arithmetic mean.

Deployment Phase

The system will be installed using the client/server network and user’s manual and training will be provided to the users.

Maintenance Phase

Maintenance is performed for two reasons. The first of these is to correct software errors and to enhance the software's capabilities in response to changing organizational needs.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the interpretation on the development of an Exhibit Repository System that manages documents and other exhibits for accreditation with two-factor authentication in wired and wireless network.

Table 1. Development of an Exhibit Repository System

Criteria	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Product Quality	4.82	Very good

The developed system has a functional document and exhibits management, secured, browser-based, multi-platform, multiuser, and user-friendly that can be used in the wired and wireless network with a computed mean of 4.82 interpreted as “Very Good”.

Table 2. Acceptable and User-friendly Graphical User Interfaces Design of the Exhibit Repository System for Accreditation

Criteria	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
User interface aesthetics	4.94	Very good

Table 2 shows the interpretation on the evaluation of the acceptable and user-friendly graphical user

interfaces of the Exhibit Repository System for Accreditation.

In terms of acceptable and user-friendly graphical interface design, ERSA has a computed mean of 4.94 which was described as “Very Good” and which further mean that the respondents agree that user interface enables pleasing and satisfying interaction to the user. Figure 2 shows the user interface and interaction design.

Figure 1. Screen Design of the System

Table 3. Experts Evaluation of the Exhibit Repository System for Accreditation

Software Quality Model	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Auditability	4.33	Very Good
Accuracy	5.00	Very Good
Completeness	4.67	Very Good
Communication Commonality	4.33	Very Good
Conciseness	5.00	Very Good
Consistency	5.00	Very Good
Observability	5.00	Very Good
Operability	4.33	Very Good
Security	5.00	Very Good
Self-Documentation	4.33	Very Good
Simplicity	5.00	Very Good
Software System		
Independence	5.00	Very Good
Traceability	5.00	Very Good
Training	5.00	Very Good
Controllability	5.00	Very Good
Data Commonality	5.00	Very Good
Decomposability	5.00	Very Good
Error Tolerance	5.00	Very Good
Execution Efficiency	5.00	Very Good
Expandability	4.67	Very Good
Generality	5.00	Very Good
Hardware Independence	5.00	Very Good
Instrumentation	5.00	Very Good
Modularity	5.00	Very Good
Overall Mean	4.86	Very Good

Table 3 shows the interpretation on the evaluation of the expert to the Exhibit Repository System for Accreditation based on McCall’s Software Quality Model.

The findings of the experts on the various areas of the Exhibit Repository System for Accreditation yielded a mean 4.86 which was described as “Very Good” which means that they agreed that the developed system was able to meet the requirements set forth by the users through the different functionalities;

Table 4. Performance of the Exhibit Repository System

Characteristics	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Functional suitability	4.77	Very Good
Performance efficiency	4.77	Very Good
Compatibility	4.76	Very Good
Reliability	4.80	Very Good
Security	4.78	Very Good
Maintainability	4.78	Very Good
Portability	4.76	Very Good
Overall Mean	4.78	Very Good

Table 4 shows the interpretation on the evaluation of the performance of the Exhibit Repository System for Accreditation.

In terms of functional suitability, ERSA has a computed mean of 4.77 which means that it has the capability to provide functions that stated and implied needs when used. In terms of performance efficiency, ERSA has a computed mean of 4.77 with verbal interpretation of “Very Good” which means that it has the capability to perform relative to the number of resources on certain conditions.

In terms of compatibility, ERSA has a computed mean of 4.76 with verbal interpretation of “Very Good” which means that it has the capability to exchange information with other component and/ or perform its required function while sharing the same hardware and software environment.

In terms of usability, ERSA has a computed mean of 4.80 with verbal description of “Very Good” which means that ERSA has the capability to be used by specified users to achieved goals with effectiveness, efficiency, and satisfaction.

In terms of reliability, the response of the respondents has a computed mean of 4.80 with verbal interpretation of “Very Good” which means that ERSA has the capability to perform specified function for a specified period of time.

In terms of security, ERSA has a computed mean of 4.78 with verbal interpretation of “Very Good”, which

means that it has the capability to protect information and data so that persons have the degree of data access appropriate to their type of level of authorization.

In terms of maintainability, ERSA has a computed mean of 4.78 with verbal interpretation of “Very Good” which means that it has the capability to be modified, to be improved, to be corrected, or the ability to adapt to changes in environment and its requirements.

In terms of portability, ERSA has a computed mean of 4.76 with verbal description of “Very Good” which means that it has the capability to operate when transferred to another usage environment;

CONCLUSIONS

After a solid and thorough investigation, as well as analyzing the problem existing in the current accreditation process of NIPSC Ajuy, the researcher-system analyst-developer had concluded that, the developed Exhibit Repository System for Accreditation collects and stores data and presents in the form of digitized documents that uses latest ICT technologies, carefully planned policies, and procedures. It has a functional document and exhibits management, secured, browser-based, multi-platform, multiuser, user-friendly and has all the features and modules that satisfy the requirements of the respondents as system users.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were highly suggested that: (1) Since computers are mostly used, especially in schools, it is highly recommended that the state universities and colleges should adapt and use the Exhibit Repository System for Accreditation; and (2) Northern Iloilo Polytechnic State College to help in the accreditation preparations during evaluation period, ERSA will serve as a digital repository that will manage the scanning, uploading, storing, duplicating, tagging, archiving and retrieving digital documents and can handle the rigorous task of handling accreditation exhibits during and after the accreditation process.

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